

SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS, BUSINESS AND INTERNATIONAL STUDIES

DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

Dr. Aristomenis Kotsakis

Doctoral Thesis

Abstract

**CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT AND SYSTEMIC MODELLING FOR THE
ASSESSMENT OF STRATEGIC ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE IN PUBLIC SECTOR ENTITIES**

Ph.D Supervisor: Professor Michael Sfakianakis

May 2019

Greece

Abstract

The current PhD-study investigates the impact of strategic organizational change on civil service employees' psychosocial well-being. Furthermore, investigates the psychosocial mechanisms explaining these effects, via a "voice of the employee" psychosocial risk management system for organizational diagnosis before, during and after the restructuring process. The study includes the investigation of the direct and indirect impacts of emergent organizational change on human capital documented by an in-depth analysis of the psychosocial cause & effect mechanisms explaining these effects. The aim is the analysis and introduction of an *agile Organizational Change Assessment Framework (OCAF)*, based on the current research findings and conclusions. The study based on the Greek COPSOQ v.3 dimensions as Organizational Change-Context and Organizational Change-Impact variables. In order to adopt a "personalised" version of this framework for every specific research sample, identification of all possible relationships and intercorrelations between the variables is necessary. To do so we examine which of these variables are the most significant in affecting the change-impact variables. This provides the means to examine any possible mediator-moderator effects between the above variables. Therefore, the main research objectives are to develop and contribute to the strategic organizational change literature, through a/an:

1. New conceptual framework and a new non-linear modelling methodology for organizational change risk assessment and longitudinal invariance measurement, based on Theory of Planned Behaviour, JDR framework & COPSOQ diagnostic instrument.
2. "Personalised" derivative framework and MODEL for practical implications in evidence-based interventions management before, during and after organizational change.
3. Implementation case study in Greece, which takes full advantage of the above theoretical and practical contributions -as a real-world implementation example- for practical implications in similar organizational change studies (organizational restructuring).

In the existing management of planned or emergent organizational change literature, many studies use a high number of variables and factors with either complex or computationally demanding models for assessing organizational change, making standard analyses (like longitudinal invariance) difficult, time consuming or not

applicable at all. This study faces that deficiency, by utilizing linear, non-linear and machine learning algorithms and structural equation modelling.

References

- Abalo, J. V. (2007). Importance values for importance-performance analysis: A formula for spreading out values derived from preference rankings. *Journal of Business Research*, 60(2), 115-121. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2006.10.009
- Ainsworth, D., & Feyerherm, A. E. (2016). Higher order change: a transorganizational system diagnostic model. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 29(5), pp. 769-781.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179-211.
- Ajzen, I. (2006). Constructing a TPB questionnaire: Conceptual and methodological considerations. Retrieved from <http://www.people.umass.edu/aizen/pdf/tpb.measurement.pdf>
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1980). *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Andersen, J. A. (2010). Assessing Public Managers' Change-Oriented Behavior: Are Private Managers Caught in the Doldrums? *International Journal of Public Administration*, 33(6), pp. 335-345.
- Anderson, P., Meyer, A., Eisenhardt, K., Carley, K., & Pettigrew, A. (1999). Introduction to the Special Issue: Applications of Complexity Theory to Organization Science. *Organization Science*, 10(3), pp. 233-236.
- Appelbaum, S. H., Profka, E., Depta, A. M., & Petrynski, B. (2018). Impact of business model change on organizational success. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 50(2), pp. 41-54.
- Appelbaum, S. H., St-Pierre, N., & Glavas, W. (1998). Strategic organizational change: the role of leadership, learning, motivation and productivity. *Management Decision*, 36(5), 289-301.

- Armenakis, A. A., & Bedeian, A. G. (1999). Organizational Change: A Review of Theory and Research in the 1990s. *Journal of Management*, 25(3), pp. 293–315.
- Armenakis, A. A., & Harris, S. G. (2002). Crafting a change message to create transformational readiness. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 15, 169-183. doi:10.1108/09534810210423080
- Armenakis, A. A., Bedeian, A. G., & Niebuhr, R. E. (1979). Planning for Organizational Intervention: The Importance of Existing Socio-Psychological Situations in Organizational Diagnosis. *Group & Organization Management*, 4(1), pp. 59-70.
- Armenakis, A. A., Bernerth, J. B., Pitts, J. P., & Walker, H. J. (2007). Organizational change recipients' beliefs scale development of an assessment instrument. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 43, 481-505.
- Armenakis, A. A., Harris, S. G., & Mossholder, K. W. (1993). Creating readiness for organizational change. *Human Relations*, 46, 681-703. doi:10.1177/001872679304600601
- Armenakis, A., & Zmud, R. (1979). Interpreting the Measurement of Change in Organizational Research. *Personnel Psychology*, pp. 709-723.
- Arnold, H. J. (1982). Moderator Variables: A Clarification of Conceptual, Analytic, and Psychometric Issues. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, pp. 143-174.
- Asplund, K., Bolander, P., & Werr, A. (2017). Achieving Strategic Change through Performance Management: The Role of Identity Threat. *Research in Organizational Change and Development*, 249-284.
- Avlonitis, G. J., Kouremenos, A., & Tzokas, N. (1994). Assessing the Innovativeness of Organizations and its Antecedents: Project Innovstrat. *European Journal of Marketing*, 28(11), 5-28.
- Baines, T., Bigdeli, A. Z., Bustinza, O. F., Shi, V. G., Baldwin, J., & Ridgway, K. (2017). Servitization: revisiting the state-of-the-art and research priorities. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 37(2), 256-278.

- Bakari, H., Hunjra, A. I., & Shabbir, G. (2017). How Does Authentic Leadership Influence Planned Organizational Change? The Role of Employees' Perceptions: Integration of Theory of Planned Behavior and Lewin's Three Step Model. *Journal of Change Management*, 17(2), pp. 155-187.
- Baker, D. (2007). *Strategic Change Management in Public Sector Organisations*. Chandos Publishing (Oxford) Limited.
- Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Sanz-Vergel, A. I. (2014). Burnout and work engagement: The JDR approach. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 1, 389-411. doi:10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-031413-091235
- Bakker, A., Albrecht, S., & Leiter, M. (2011). Key questions regarding work engagement. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 20(1), pp. 4-28.
- Bakker, B. A. (2017). Job demands–resources theory: Taking stock and looking forward. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, Vol 22(3), 273-285.
- Bargal, D., Gold, M., & Lewin, M. (1992). Introduction: The heritage of Kurt Lewin. *Journal of Social Issues*, 48(2), 3-13. doi:10.1111/j.1540-4560.1992.tb00879.x
- Barnett, C. K., & Pratt, M. G. (2000). From threat-rigidity to flexibility - Toward a learning model of autogenic crisis in organizations. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 13(1), pp. 74-88.
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research. conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173-1182. doi:doi:10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research. conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), , 1173-1182. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173
- Baruch, Y., & Ramalho, N. (2006). Communalities and Distinctions in the Measurement of Organizational Performance and Effectiveness Across For-

- Profit and Nonprofit Sectors. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 35(1), 39-65.
- Becker, J.-M. K. (2012). Hierarchical Latent Variable Models in PLS-SEM: Guidelines for Using Reflective-Formative Type Models. *Long Range Planning*, 45 (5-6), 359–394.
- Beckhard, R. (1975). *Strategies for Large Systems Change* (Vol. 16(2)). Sloan Management Review.
- Beer, M., & Nohria, N. (2000, May/June). Cracking the code of change. pp. ,133-141.
- Beeri, I. (2011). Turnaround management strategies in public systems: the impact on group-level organizational citizenship behavior. *International Review of Administrative Science* 2012, 78(1), pp. 158-179.
- Bentler, P. M. (1988). *Causal modeling via structural equation systems*. In J. R. Nesselroade & R. B. Cattell (Eds.). New York: NY: Plenum Press.
- Bentler, P. M., & Bonett, D. G. . (1980). Significance tests and goodness of fit in the analysis of covariance structures. *Psychological Bulletin*, 88(3), 588-606.
- Berthelsen, H., Conway, P. M., & Clausen, T. (2018). Is organizational justice climate at the workplace associated with individual-level quality of care and organizational affective commitment? A multi-level, cross-sectional study on dentistry in Sweden. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*(91), pp. 237–245.
- Berthelsen, H., Hakanen, J., & Westerlund, H. (2018). Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire -A validation study using the Job Demand-Resources model. *PLoS ONE*, 13(4).
- Berthelsen, H., Westerlund, H., Hakanen, J. J., & Kristensen, T. S. (2017). It is not just about occupation, but also about where you work. *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, pp. 372–379.
- Bhattacharjee, A. (2012). *Social science research : Principles, Methods and Practices*. Tampa: University of South Florida.
- Bisogno, M., Citro, F., Santis, S., & Tommasetti, A. (2017). Disclosure Quality Measurement in the Public Sector: A Structured Literature Review. *Journal of Business and Management*, 12(12).
- Blanchard, K. (2008). *Ηγεσία σε υψηλότερο επίπεδο*. ,ΕΚΔΟΣΕΙΣ ΚΛΕΙΔΑΡΙΘΜΟΣ.

- Bollen, K. A. (1989b). A new incremental fit index for general structural equation models. *Sociological Methods & Research*, *17*, 303-316.
- Bordia, P. H. (2004). Uncertainty during organisational change: Is it all about control? *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, *13*, 345-365.
- Bordia, P., Hobman, E., Jones, E., Gallois, C., & Callan, V. J. (2004). Uncertainty during Organizational Change: Types, Consequences and Management Strategies. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, *18*(4), pp. 507-532.
- Bornmann, L., & Mutz, R. (2015). Growth rates of modern science: A bibliometric analysis based on the number of publications and cited references. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, *66*(11), 2215-2222.
- Boss, R. W., Dunford, B. B., Boss, A. D., & McConkie, M. L. (2010). Sustainable Change in the Public Sector: The Longitudinal Benefits of Organization Development. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, *46*(4), 436-472.
- Boxman, E. A., De Graaf, P. M., & Flap, H. D. (1991). The impact of social and human capital on the income attainment of Dutch managers. *Social Networks*, *13*, 51-73.
- Boyne, G. A. (2006). Strategies for Public Service Turnaround: Lessons From the Private Sector? *Administration & Society*, *38*(3), pp. 365-388.
- Breevaart, K., & Bakker, A. B. (2018). Daily job demands and employee work engagement: The role of daily transformational leadership behavior. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, *23*(3), 338-349. doi:10.1037/ocp0000082
- Breiman, L. (2001). Random forests. *Machine Learning*(45), 5-32.
- Burnes, B. (2004). Kurt Lewin and the Planned Approach to Change: A Re-appraisal. *Journal of Management Studies*, *41*(6).
- Burnes, B., & Cooke, B. (2012). The past, present and future of organization development: Taking the long view. *Human Relations* *65*(11), 65(11), 1395-.
- By, R. T., Kuipers, B., & Procter, S. (2018). Understanding Teams in Order to Understand Organizational Change: The OTIC Model of Organizational Change. *Journal of Change Management*, *18*(1), pp. 1-9.
- Campbell, D. T., & Stanley, J. (1963). Experimental and quasi-experimental designs for research.

- Candolo, C., Davison, A. C., & Demétrio, C. G. B. (2003). A note on model uncertainty in linear regression. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series D: The Statistician*, 52(2), 165-177. doi:10.1111/1467-9884.00349
- Canty, A. J., & Davison, A. C. (1999). Resampling-based variance estimation for labour force surveys. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series D: The Statistician*, 48(3), 379-391. doi:10.1111/1467-9884.00196
- Canty, A. J., Davison, A. C., Hinkley, D. V., & Ventura, V. (2006). Bootstrap diagnostics and remedies. *Canadian Journal of Statistics*, 34(1), 5-27. doi:10.1002/cjs.5550340103
- Carter, M. Z., Armenakis, A., Feild, H., & Mossholder, K. W. (2013). Transformational leadership, relationship quality, and employee performance during continuous incremental organizational change. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*(34), pp. 942–958.
- Charitou, C., & Markides, C. (2003). *How To Respond to Disruptive Strategic Market Leader*. London Business School.
- Chaudary, A., Fatima, A., & Zafar, F. (2014). Strategic Change: The Influence of Managerial Characteristics and Organizational Growth. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 5(2), pp. 535-542.
- Chepkemoi N., M Moronge. (2015). Challenges hindering effective strategic change management in counties in Kenya: a case of Nairobi County. *Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*.
- Chiao, G. (2000). Multilevel Issues and Culture. an Integrative View. In K. Klein, & S. Kozlowski (Eds.), *Multilevel Theory, Research, and Methods in Organizations. Foundations, Extensions and New Directions*.
- Chin, E. B. (1988). Multivariate two stage test based on ranks. *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods*, 17(12), 4099-4119. doi:10.1080/03610928808829860
- Cinite, I., & Duxbury, L. E. (2018). Measuring the Behavioral Properties of Commitment and Resistance to Organizational Change. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 54(2), 113–.

- Cohen, J. (1988). Set correlation and contingency tables. *Applied Psychological Measurement, 12*(4), 425-434. doi:10.1177/014662168801200410
- Cohen, J. (1988). Set correlation and contingency tables. *Applied Psychological Measurement, 12*(4), 425-434. doi:10.1177/014662168801200410
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2007). *Research Methods in Education*. New York: Routledge.
- Collins, J. (2006). *Good to Great and the Social Sectors (Why business thinking is not the answer)*. Random House Business Books.
- Collm, A., & Schedler, K. (2014). Strategies for introducing organizational innovation to public service organizations. *Public Management Review, 16*(1), 140-161. doi:doi:10.1080/14719037.2013.822528
- Coons, M. H. (2012). *Change is Constant: The ongoing reengineering of senior administration in community college*. Dissertations. Paper 53.
- Cullen, K. L., Edwards, B. D., Casper, W. C., & Gue, K. R. (2014). Employees' Adaptability and Perceptions of Change-Related Uncertainty: Implications for Perceived Organizational Support, Job Satisfaction, and Performance. *J Bus Psychol, 29*, 269–280.
- Cullen-Lester, K. L., Webster, B. D., Edwards, B. D., & Braddy, P. (2019). The effect of multiple negative, neutral, and positive organizational changes. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology, 28*(1), 124-135.
- Cummings, S., & Zanotti, . F. (2016). Ethos as the New Strategic Resource. *International Journal of Public and Private Management, 2*(2).
- Cummings, S., Bridgman, T., & Brown, K. G. (2016). Unfreezing change as three steps: Rethinking Kurt Lewin's legacy for change management. *Human Relations, 69*(1), 33-60. doi:doi:10.1177/0018726715577707
- Davenport, T. (2005). The Coming Commoditization of Processes. *Harvard Business Review*.
- Davison, A. C., and Hinkley, D. V. (1997). *Bootstrap Methods and Their Application*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Davison, A. C., Hinkley, D. V., & Worton, B. J. (1992). Bootstrap likelihoods. *Biometrika, 79*(1), 113-130. doi:10.1093/biomet/79.1.113

- Davison, A. C., Hinkley, D. V., & Young, G. A. (2003). Recent developments in bootstrap methodology. *Statistical Science*, *18*(2), 141-157. doi:10.1214/ss/1063994969
- De Jong, T., Wiezer, N., De Weerd, M., Nielsen, K., Mattila-Holappa, P., & Mockało, Z. (2016). The impact of restructuring on employee wellbeing: a systematic review of longitudinal studies. *Work & Stress*, *30*(1), pp. 91-114.
- De Jongea, J., Bosma, H., Peter, R., & Siegrist, J. (2000). Job strain, effort-reward imbalance and employee well-being: a large-scale cross-sectional study. *Social Science & Medicine*, pp. 1317-1327.
- De Vries, H., Bekkers, V., & Tummers, L. (2016). Innovation in the Public Sector: A Systematic Review and Future Research Agenda. *Public Administration*, *94*(1), pp. 146–166.
- de Vries, M. F. (2013). The Eight Archetypes of Leadership 2013. *Harvard Business Review*.
- Dede, S., & Sfakianakis, M. (2014). The new technologies in the developments and reorganization of public organization. *International Journal of Economic Research*, *11*(1), , 115-126.
- der Voet, J. V., Kuipers, B. S., & Groene, S. (2016). Implementing Change in Public Organizations: The relationship between leadership and affective commitment to change in a public sector context. *Public Management Review*, *18*(6), pp. 842-865.
- Desmarchelier, B., Djellal, F., & Gallou, F. (2018). *Public Service Innovation Networks (PSINs): Collaborating for Innovation and Value Creation*. Research Report Université de Lille.
- Devos, G., Buelens, M., & Bouckennooghe, D. (2007). Contribution of Content, Context, and Process to Understanding Openness to Organizational Change: Two Experimental Simulation Studies. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, *147*(6), 607-630.
- di Pofi, J. (2002). Organizational diagnostics: integrating qualitative and quantitative methodology. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, *15*(2), 156-168.

- Di Tecco, C., Jain, A., Valenti, A., Iavicoli, S., & Leka, S. (2017). An evaluation of the impact of a policy-level intervention to address psychosocial risks on organisational action in Italy. *Safety Science*(100), pp. 103–109.
- Dijkstra, T. K., & Henseler, J. (2015). Consistent partial least squares path modeling. *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems*, 39(2), 297-316. doi:doi:10.25300/MISQ/2015/39.2.02
- Dorling, J. L. (2017). Impact of psychological capital on the resistance to change during post-merger integration: A theoretical model". *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 30(6), pp. 936-956.
- Dupret, E., Bocéréan, C., Teherani, M., Feltrin, M., & Pejtersen, J. H. (2012). Psychosocial risk assessment: French validation of the Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire (COPSOQ). *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*(40), pp. 482–490.
- Dutton, J., & Duncan, R. (1987). The creation of momentum for change through the process of strategic issue diagnosis. *Strategic Management Journal*, 8, 279-295.
- Dutton, J., Fahey, L., & Narayanan, V. (1983). Towards Understanding Strategic Issue Diagnosis. *Strategic Management Journal*, pp. 307-323.
- Efron, B., & Tibshirani, R. (1986). Bootstrap methods for standard errors, confidence intervals, and other measures of statistical accuracy. *Statistical Science*, 1(1), 54-75. doi:doi:10.1214/ss/1177013815
- Eikeland, O., & Nicolini, D. (2011). Turning practically: broadening the horizon",. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 24(2), pp. 164-174.
- Erwin, D. G., & Garman, A. N. (2010). Resistance to organizational change: linking research and practice. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 31(1), 39-56.
- Fattore, G., Iacovone, D., & Steccolini, I. (2018). Managing successful change in the public sector': a view from the consultants' world. *Public Management Review*, 20(4), 587-606.
- Favero, N., Kenneth J., M., & O'Toole Jr, L. J. (2016). Goals, Trust, Participation, and Feedback: Linking Internal Management With Performance Outcomes. *Journal of Public Administration Research And Theory*, pp. 327–343.

- Ferlie, E., Hartley, J., & Martin, S. (2003). Changing Public Service Organizations: Current Perspectives and Future Prospects. *British Journal of Management*(14), pp. S1–S14.
- Fernandes, C., & Pereira, A. (2016). Exposure to psychosocial risk factors in the context of work: a systematic review. *Rev. Saúde Pública*, 50.
- Fernandez, S., & Rainey, H. G. (2006). Managing Successful Organizational Change in the Public Sector. *Public Administration Review* .
- Ferreira, A., Cardoso, C., & Braun, T. (2018). The mediating effects of ego-resilience in the relationship between organizational support and resistance to change. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 13(1), pp. 104-124.
- Fong, T. C., Ho, R. T., Au-Yeung, F. S., Sing, C., Law, K., Lee, L., & Ng, S. (2016). The relationships of change in work climate with changes in burnout and depression: a 2-year longitudinal study of Chinese mental health care workers. *Psychology, Health & Medicine*, 21:4,, 21(4), pp. 401-412.
- Ford, J. (2010). Studying Leadership Critically : A Psychosocial Lens on Leadership Identities. *Leadership*, pp. 47-65.
- Foster, R. D. (2010). Resistance, Justice, and Commitment to Change. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 21(1).
- Frost, J. (2013). Regression Analysis: How do I Interpret R-squared and Assess the Goodness-of-Fit? . Retrieved from <http://blog.minitab.com/blog/adventures-in-statistics/regression-analysis-how-do-i-interpret-r-squared-and-assess-the-goodness-of-fit>
- Gerbec, M. (2017). Safety change management – A new method for integrated management of organizational and technical changes. *Safety Science*, pp. 225–234.
- Ghayour B., S. M., & Doaei, M. (2012). A Dialectic Model of Development of Stakeholders' Theory and Corporate Governance: from Hume Utilitarianism to Aristotelian Virtue Ethics. *International Journal of Financial Research*, 3(2).
- Gilmour, S. G. (1996). The Interpretation of Mallows's C_p -Statistic . *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series D (The Statistician)*, 45, 49-56. doi:DOI: 10.2307/2348411

- Ginsberg, A. (1988). Measuring and Modelling Changes in Strategy :Theoretical Foundations and Empirical Directions. *Strategic Management Journal*(9), pp. 559-575.
- Glavopoulos, E., Bersimis, S., Georgakellos, D., & Sfakianakis, M. (2014). Investigating the factors affecting companies' attitudes towards CSR and CER during the fiscal crisis in greece. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*,, 57(11), 1612-1641. doi:doi:10.1080/09640568.2013.826577
- Godin, G., & Kok, G. (1996). The theory of planned behavior: A review of its applications to health-related behaviors. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 11, 87-98.
- Graetz, F., & Smith, A. C. (2010). Managing Organizational Change:A Philosophies of Change Approach. *Journal of Change Management*, 10(2), pp. 135-154.
- H. Bunke & B. Droge. (2007, July 05). A stepwise procedure for the selection of nonlinear regression models. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02331888508801822>
- Hagemeister, A., & Volmer, J. (2017)). Do social conflicts at work affect employees' job satisfaction? : The moderating role of emotion regulation",. *International Journal of Conflict Management*.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., and Sarstedt, M. . (2017). A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). (2nd). Sage: Thousand Oaks. Retrieved from <http://www.pls-sem.com>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., and Thiele, K. O. (forthcoming).
• Mirror, Mirror on the Wall: A Comparative Evaluation of Composite-based Structural Equation Modeling Methods, . *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., and Gudergan S. P. . (2018). Advanced Issues in Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). *Sage: Thousand Oaks*.
- Håkansson, M., Dellve, L., Waldenström, M., & Holden, R. J. (2017). Sustained lean transformation of working conditions: A Swedish longitudinal case study. *Hum. FactorsMan*. 2017(27), pp. 268–279.

- Hamilton, R. P. (2010). The concept of health: beyond normativism and naturalism1. *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice*, pp. 323–329.
- Handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators. Methodology and user guide.* (2008). 2, rue André-Pascal, 75775 PARIS CEDEX 16: OECD PUBLICATIONS.
- Hanscome, R., Davies, J., & Poitevin, H. (2017). *Apply Voice-of-the-Customer Best Practices to Voice-of-the-Employee Initiatives.*
- Harrell, F. E., Jr., Lee, K. L., Califf, R. M., Pryor, D. B., & Rosati, R. A. (1984). Regression modelling strategies for improved prognostic prediction. *Statistics in Medicine*, 3(2), 143-152. doi:10.1002/sim.4780030207
- Hassard, J., Teoh, K., & Cox, T. (2017). Organizational uncertainty and stress among teachers in Hong Kong: work characteristics and organizational justice. *Health Promotion International*, pp. 860-870.
- Hauser, F. (Ed.). (2017). *Quality of Public Administration. A Toolbox for Practitioners.* Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Hayes, A. F., & Preacher, K. J. (2014). Statistical mediation analysis with a multicategorical independent variable. *British Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Psychology*, 67(3), 451-470. doi:10.1111/bmsp.12028
- Hayes, A. F., & Preacher, K. J. (2014). Statistical mediation analysis with a multicategorical independent variable. *British Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Psychology*, 67(3), , 451-470. doi:doi:10.1111/bmsp.12028
- Henseler, J., and Sarstedt, M. (2013). Goodness-of-Fit Indices for Partial Least Squares Path Modeling. *Computational Statistics*, 28(2), 565-580.
- Henseler, J., Dijkstra, T. K., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., Diamantopoulos, A., Straub, D. W., . . . Calantone, R. J. (2014). Common beliefs and reality about PLS: Comments on rönkkö and evermann. *Organizational Research Methods*, 17(2),, 182-209. doi:10.1177/1094428114526928
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The use of partial least squares path modeling in international marketing. doi:10.1108/S1474-7979(2009)0000020014
- Herman, J., & Usher, W. (2017). SALib: An open-source Python library for Sensitivity Analysis. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 2(9).

- Hu, L., & Bentler, P. M. (1998). (n.d.). Fit indices in covariance structure modeling: Sensitivity to underparameterized model misspecification. *Psychological Methods*, 3(4), 424-453. doi:10.1037/1082-989X.3.4.424
- Hulme, E. W. (1923). *Statistical bibliography in relation to the growth of modern civilization*. London.
- Jaros, S. (2010). Commitment to Organizational Change: A Critical Review. *Journal of Change Management*, 10(1), pp. 79-108.
- Jefferson, R. N. (2014). Action Research: Theory and Applications. *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 20(2), pp. 91-116.
- Jian, G. (2007). Unpacking Unintended Consequences in Planned Organizational Change A Process Model. *Communication Quarterly*, 21(1), 5-28.
- Jimmieson, N. L. (2008). Utilizing the theory of planned behavior to inform change management: An investigation of employee intentions to support organizational change. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 44, 237-262. doi:10.1177/0021886307312773
- Jimmieson, N. L., Terry, D. J., & Callan, V. J. (2004). A longitudinal study of employee adaptation to organizational change: The role of change-related information and change-related self-efficacy. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 9. doi:10.1037/10768998.9.1.11
- Jimmieson, N. L., White, K. M., & Zajdlewicz, L. (2009). Psychosocial predictors of intentions to engage in change supportive behaviors in an organizational context. *Journal of Change Management*, 9, 233-250. doi:10.1080/14697010903125472
- Johnson, B., & Cristensen, L. (2012). *Educational Research. Quantitative, Qualitative and Mixed Research Approaches*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Kidron, A., Ofek, Y., & Cohen, H. (2016). (2016) "New perspective on the black box of internal auditing and organisational change. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 31(8/9), 804-820.
- Kim, S., & Wang, J. (2018). The role of job demands–resources (JDR) between service workers’ emotional labor and burnout: New directions for labor policy at local

- government. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(12) . doi:doi:10.3390/ijerph15122894
- Klein, P. G., Mahoney, J. T., McGahan, A. M., & Pitelis, C. N. (2013). Capabilities and value in public organizations . *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*(7), 70–91.
- Kothari, C. (2004). *Research methodology.Methods and Techniques*. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
- Kotsakis & Nübling et.al. (2018). COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece. Leuven, Belgium: Employability in the 21st Century: 2nd International Conference on Sustainable Employability. Building Bridges between Science and Practice.
- Kotsakis, A., Thanopoulos, J., Kallimanis, S., & Lentas, I. (2016). Strategic cultural change: A real world application example in the public sector. *European mmeetings on cybernetics and systems research*.
- Kotter, J. (1995). Leading change: Why transformation efforts fail. *Harvard Business Review*, 73(2), pp. 59–67.
- Koukoulaki, T., Pinotsi, D., Georgiadou, P., Daikou, A., Targoutzidis, A., Poullos, K., . . . Pahkin, K. (2017). Restructuring seriously damages well-being of workers: The case of the restructuring programme in local administration in Greece. *Safety Science*, 100, pp. 30–36.
- Kozlowski, S., & Klein, K. (2000). A multilevel approach to theory and research in organizations. Contextual, temporal, and Emergent Processes. In K. Klein, & S. Kozlowski (Eds.), *Multilevel Theory, Research, and Methods in Organizations. Foundations, Extensiions and New Directions*. Jossey Bass.
- Kristensen, T. (2010). A questionnaire is more than a questionnaire. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*, 38(3), pp. 149–155.
- Kuipers, B. (2009). Performability of Work Teams: Balancing Hard and Soft Issues. *International Journal of Performability Engineering*, 5(2), 143-151.
- Kuipers, B. S., & Giurge, L. M. (2017). Does alignment matter? The performance implications of HR roles connected to organizational strategy. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 28(22), pp. 3179-3201.

- Kuipers, B. S., Higgs, M., Kickert, W., Tummers, L., Grandia, J., & van der Voet, J. (2014). The management of change in public organization : A literature review. *Public Administration*, 92(1), 1-20.
- Kuipers, B., Higgs, M., Kickert, W., Tummers, L., Grandia, J., & Van der Voet, J. (Forthcoming). The management of change in public organisations: A literature review. *Public Administration*.
- Land, C., & Śliwa, M. (2009). The novel and organization: introduction from the Editors. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 22(4), pp. 349-356.
- Lawrie, G., & Cobbold, I. (2004). Third-generation balanced scorecard: evolution of an effective strategic control tool. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 53(7), 611-623.
- Leighninger, M. (2013). *Using Online Tools to Engage – and be Engaged by –The Public Deliberative Democracy Consortium*. IBM Center for the Business of Government.
- Leka, S., & Cox, T. (2008). *PRIMA-EF : Guidance on the European Framework for Psychosocial Risk Management: A resource for Employers and Workers Representatives*. WHO.
- Levinson H., Andrew G. Spohn, Janice Molinari. (1972). Organizational Diagnosis.
- Levinson, H. (1972, September-October). Easing the pain of personal loss. *Harvard Business Review*, 50:5, 80-88.
- Levinson, H. (2002). *Organizational Assessment: A Step-by-Step Guide to Effective Consulting*. Washington. D.C.: American Psychological Association.
- Lewin, K. (1947). Frontiers in group dynamics. *Human Relations*(1), pp. 5–41.
- Loh, M. Y., Idris, M. A., Dollard, M. F., & Isahak, M. (2018). Psychosocial safety climate as a moderator of the moderators: Contextualizing JDR models and emotional demands effects. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 91(3), 620-644. doi: doi:10.1111/joop.12211
- Lohmöller, J. (1989). Predictive vs. Structural Modeling: PLS vs. ML. In: Latent Variable Path Modeling with Partial Least Squares. *Physica*.

- Lynch, S. E., & Mors, M. L. (2019). Strategy implementation and organizational change: How formal reorganization affects professional networks. *Long Range Planning*, 52(2), 255-270. doi:doi:10.1016/j.lrp.2018.02.003
- MacKillop, E. (2018). Leadership in organisational change: A post-structuralist research agenda. *Organization*, 25(2), pp. 205–222.
- Makri, E., & Ntalianis, F. (2015). Post M&A ill-health. *Employee Relations*, pp. 176-191.
- Makridakis, S., & Bakas, N. (2015). Forecasting and uncertainty: A survey. *Risk and Decision Analysis* , pp. 1–28.
- Martono, S., Wulansari, N. A., Putri, V. W., & Khoiruddin, M. (2018). Psychological Mechanism Explaining the Effect of HR Practices Towards Employee Performance (A Study in Public Higher Education). *International Conference on Economics, Business and Economic Education* .
- Mathiassen, W. K. (2011). Explicit and implicit theories of change when designing and implementing preventive ergonomics interventions – a systematic literature review. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*, 37(5), pp. 363-375.
- McFillen, J. M., O'Neil, D. A., Balzer, W. K., & Varney, G. H. (2013). Organizational Diagnosis: An Evidence-based Approach. *Journal of Change Management*, 13(2), pp. 223-246.
- McKay, V. R., Morshed, A. B., Brownson, R. C., Proctor, E. K., & Prusaczyk, B. (2018). Letting Go: Conceptualizing Intervention De-implementation in Public Health and Social Service Settings. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 1–14.
- McMurray, A., Pirola-Merlo, A., Sarros, J., & Islam, M. (2010). Leadership, climate, psychological capital, commitment, and wellbeing in a non-profit organization. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 31(5), 436-457.
- Meyer, J. P., Hecht, T. D., Gill, H., & Toplonysky, L. (2010). Person–organization (culture) fit and employee commitment under conditions of organizational change: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 76, pp. 458–473.

- Mintzberg, H., & Westley, F. (1992). Cycles of Organizational Change. *Strategic Management Journal*(13), pp. 39-59.
- Muchran, M., & Pagalung, G. (2018). Empirical Studies Use The Balanced Scorecard To Measure Government Performance. *Archives of Business Research*, 6(10), 228-233.
- Mudrak, J., Zabrodska, K., Kveton, P., Jelinek, M., Blatny, M., Solcova, I., & Machovcova, K. (2018). Occupational well-being among university faculty: A job demands-resources model. *Research in Higher Education*, 59(3), 325-348. doi:doi:10.1007/s11162-017-9467-x
- Muriel, G., Dimopoulos, I., & Lek, S. (2003). Review and comparison of methods to study the contribution of variables in artificial neural network models. *Ecological modelling*, 160(3), 249-264.
- Neumann, W., & Village, J. (n.d.). Ergonomics action research II: a framework for integrating HF into work system design. *Ergonomics*, 55(10), pp. 1140-1156.
- Nielsen, K., & Randall, R. (2013). Opening the black box: Presenting a model for evaluating organizational-level interventions. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 22(3), 601-617.
- Nübling, M., & Hasselhorn, H. M. (2010). The Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire in Germany: From the validation of the instrument to the formation of a job-specific database of psychosocial factors at work. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*(38), pp. 120–124.
- Nytrø, K., Saksvik, P. Ø., Mikkels, A., Bohle, P., & Quinlan, M. (2000). An appraisal of key factors in the implementation of occupational stress interventions. *Work & Stress*, 14(3), pp. 213-225.
- Olden, J. D., & Jackson, D. A. (2002). Illuminating the “black box”: a randomization approach for understanding variable contributions in artificial neural networks. *Ecological modelling*, 154(1-2), 135-150.
- Oreg, S., Vakola, M., & Armenakis, A. (2011). Change Recipients’ Reactions to Organizational Change: A 60-Year Review of Quantitative Studies,. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 47(4), pp. 461-564.

- Pardo del Val, M., & Fuentes, C. M. (2003). Resistance to change: a literature review and empirical study. *Management Decision*, 41(2), pp. 148-155.
- Parker, C. P., Baltes, B. B., Young, S. A., Huff, J. W., Altmman, R. A., Lacost, H. A., & Roberts, J. E. (2003). Relationships between psychological climate perceptions and work outcomes:a meta-analytic review. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 24, 389–416.
- Paulsen, N., Callan, V. J., Grice, T. A., Rooney, D., Gallois, C., Jones, E., . . . Bordia, P. (2005). Job uncertainty and personal control during downsizing: A comparison of survivors and victims. *Human Relations*, 58(4), pp. 463–496.
- Peng, D. X., & Lai, F. (2012). Using partial least squares in operations management research: A practical guideline and summary of past research. *Journal of Operations Management*, 30(6), 467-480. doi:10.1016/j.jom.2012.06.002
- Pihla, P., Albertsenb, K., Hoghc, A., & Andersen, L. P. (2017). Social capital and workplace bullying,. *Work*, 57, pp. 535–545.
- Plevris, V., Bakas, N., Markeset, G., & Bellos, J. (2017). Literature review of masonry structures under earthquake excitation utilizing machine learning algorithms. *6th International Conference COMPDYN*.
- Pollitt, C. (2010). Cuts and Reforms – Public Services as we Move into a new Era. *Society and Economy* 32.(1), pp. 17–31.
- Pollitt, C., & Dan, S. (2011). *The impacts of the New Public Management in Europe: A meta analysis*. European Research Area.
- Pritchard, A. (1969). *Journal of Documentation*, 25(4), 348–349.
- Pye, A., & Pettigrew, A. (2006). Strategizing and Organizing: Change as a Political Learning Process, Enabled by Leadership. *Long Range Planning*(39), pp. 583-590.
- Rafferty, A. E., & Restubog, S. L. (2010). The Impact of Change Process and Context on Change Reactions and Turnover During a Merger. *Journal of Management*, 36(5), 1309-1338.
- Rafferty, A. E., Jimmieson, N. L., & Armenakis, A. A. (2013). Change Readiness: A Multilevel Review. *Journal of Management*, 39(1).

- Raineri, A. B. (2011). Change management practices: Impact on perceived change results. *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 64(3), 266-272. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2009.11.011>
- Rajagopalan, N., & Spreitzer, G. (1996). Towards a Theory of Strategic Change : A multi-lens perspective and integrative framework. *CEO Publication*.
- Ravalier, J. M., McVicar, A., & Munn-Giddings, C. (2014). Public service stress and burnout over 12 months. *Occupational Medicine* (64), pp. 521–523.
- Raye, J. (2014). Fractal Organisation Theory. *Journal of Organisational Transformation & Social Change*, 11(1), pp. 50-68.
- Rees C., Kerstin Alfes & Mark Gatenby. (2013). Employee voice and engagement: connections and consequences,. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*,, 24:14, 2780-2798. doi:DOI: 10.1080/09585192.2013.763843
- Rees, C. J., & Johari, H. (2010). (2010) "Senior managers' perceptions of the HRM function during times of strategic organizational change: Case study evidence from a public sector banking institution in Malaysia. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 23(5), 517-536.
- Ricci, V. (2005). Fitting distributions with R. doi: <http://cran.r-project.org/doc/contrib/Ricci-distributions-en.pdf>
- Richard D. Riley Kym I.E. Snell Joie Ensor Danielle L. Burke Frank E. Harrell Jr Karel G.M. Moons Gary S. Collins. (2018). Minimum sample size for developing a multivariable prediction model: Part I – Continuous outcomes. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.7993>
- Ringle, C.M./ Sarstedt, M.: . (2016). Gain More Insight from Your PLS-SEM Results: The Importance-Performance Map Analysis,. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 119 (9), 1865-1886.
- Rosenbaum, D., More, E., & Steane, P. (n.d.). Planned organisational change management: Forward to the past? An exploratory literature review". *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 31(2), pp. 286-303.
- Rousseau, D. (2000). Multilevel Competencies and Missing Linkages. In K. Klein, & S. Kozlowski (Eds.), *Multilevel Theory, Research, and Methods in Organizations. Foundations, Extensions and New Directions*. Jossey Bass.

- Saksvik, P., Tvedt, S. D., Nytrø, K., Andersen, G. R., Andersen, T. K., Buvik, M. P., & Torvatn, H. (2007). Developing criteria for healthy organizational change. *Work & Stress, 21*(3), pp. 243-263.
- Schiro, J. B., & Baker, R. L. (2013). Downsizing and Organizational Change Survivors and Victims : Mental Health Issues. *The International Journal of Applied Management and Technology, 7*(1).
- Seijts, G. H., & Roberts, M. (2011). The impact of employee perceptions on change in a municipal government. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal, 32*(2), 190-213.
- Sfakianakis, M. E., & Verginis, D. G. (2008). (2008). A new family of nonparametric quantile estimators. *Communications in Statistics: Simulation and Computation, 37*(2), 337-345. doi:10.1080/03610910701790491
- Siegal, W., Church, A. H., Javitch, M., Waclawski, J., Burd, S., Bazigos, M., . . . Burke, W. W. (1996). Understanding the management of change: An overview of managers' perspectives and assumptions in the 1990s. *Journal of Organizational Change Management, 9*(6), 54-80.
- Silva, Ringle & Ringle, Christian & Silva, Dirceu & Bido, Diogenes. (2014). STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING WITH THE SMARTPLS. *Revista Brasileira de Marketing, 13*, 56 -73. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281448905_STRUCTUREL_EQUATION_MODELING_WITH_THE_SMARTPLS
- Sminia, H. (2016). Pioneering Process Research: Andrew Pettigrew's Contribution to Management Scholarship, 1962–2014. *International Journal of Management Reviews, 18*, pp. 111–132.
- Smollan, R. K. (2015). Causes of stress before, during and after organizational change: a qualitative study. *Journal of Organizational Change Management, 28*(2), pp. 301-314.
- Smollan, R. K. (2015). The Personal Costs of Organizational Change: A Qualitative Study. *Public Performance & Management Review, 39*(1), pp. 223-247.
- Smollan, R. K. (2017). Supporting staff through stressful organizational change. *Human Resource Development International, 20*(4), pp. 282-304.

- Snezana, Z., Miodrag, M., & Tomislav, R. (2017). Psychosocial Risk Management. *Safety Engineering*, pp. 93-98.
- Somekh, B., & Zeichner, K. (2009). Action research for educational reform:remodelling action research theories and practices in local contexts. *Educational Action Research*, 17(1), pp. 5-21.
- Spitzmueller, M. C. (2018). (2018) Remaking “Community” Mental Health:Contested Institutional Logics and Organizational Change. *Human Service Organizations : Management, Leadership & Governance*, 42(2), 123-145.
- Stauder, A., Nistor, K., Zakor, T., Szabó, A., Nistor, A., Ádám, S., & Thege, B. K. (2017). Quantifying Multiple Work-Related Psychosocial Risk Factors:Proposal for a Composite Indicator Based on the COPSOQ II. *Int.J. Behav. Med.*
- Straatmann, T., Kohnke, O., Hattrup, K., & Mueller, K. (2016). Assessing Employees’ Reactions to Organizational Change: An Integrative Framework of Change-Specific and Psychological Factors. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 52(3), 265–295.
- Swanson, V., & Power, K. (2001). Employees' perceptions of organizational restructuring: The role of social support. *Work & Stress*, 15(2), pp. 161-178.
- Tenenhaus, M. (2008). Component-based structural equation modelling. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*, 19(7-8), 871-886. doi:10.1080/14783360802159543
- Tenenhaus, M., Amato, S., and Esposito Vinzi, V. (2004). A Global Goodness-of-Fit Index for PLS Structural Equation Modeling. *Proceedings of the XLII SIS Scientific Meeting*, 739-742.
- Tenenhaus, M., Vinzi, V. E., Chatelin, Y. -, & Lauro, C. (2005). PLS path modeling. *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis*, 48(1), 159-205. doi:10.1016/j.csda.2004.03.005
- Teng, J., Grover, V., & Fiedler, K. (1996). Developing Strategic Perspectives on Business Process Reengineering:From Process Reconfiguration to Organizational Change. *Omega, Int. J. Mgmt Sci.*, 24(3), 271-294.

- Thugi, L. W., & Gathenya, J. (2018). Influence of strategic change on employee performance: Case study of directorate of immigration services Kenya. *Journal of International Business, Innovation and Strategic Management*, 1(7), 249 - 269.
- Tourish, D., Paulsen, N., Hobman, E., & Bordia, P. (2004). The Downsides of Downsizing: Communication Processes and Information Needs in the Aftermath of a Workforce Reduction Strategy. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 17(4), 485-516.
- Vakola, M. (2016). The reasons behind change recipients' behavioral reactions: a longitudinal investigation. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 31(1), pp. 202-215.
- Vakola, M., & Petrou, P. (2018). *Organizational Change: Psychological effects and strategies for coping*. 2 Park Square, Milton Park, Abingdon, Oxon OX14 4RN: Routledge.
- van de Ven, A. H., & Huber, G. P. (1990). (1990) Longitudinal Field Research Methods for Studying Processes of Organizational Change. *Organization Science*, 1(3), 213-219.
- van de Ven, A. H., & Huber, G. P. (1990). Longitudinal Field Research Methods for Studying Processes of Organizational Change. *Organization Science*, 1(3), 213-219.
- Van den Heuvel, M. I., Demerouti, E., & Bakker, A. B. (2014). How psychological resources facilitate adaptation to organizational change. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 23(6), pp. 847-858.
- van den Oord, A., Elliott, K., van Witteloostuijn, A., Barlage, M., Polos, L., & Rogiest, S. (2017). A cognitive organization theory (COT) of organizational change: Measuring organizational texture, audience appeal, and leadership engagement. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 30(6), pp. 903-922.
- Van der Voet, J., & Vermeeren, B. (2017). Change Management in Hard Times: Can Change Management Mitigate the Negative Relationship Between Cutbacks and the Organizational Commitment and Work Engagement of Public Sector Employees? *American Review of Public Administration*, 47(2), pp. 230–252.

- Van der Voet, J., Groeneveld, S., & Kuipers, B. S. (2014). Talking the Talk or Walking the Walk? The Leadership of Planned and Emergent Change in a Public Organization. *Journal of Change Management*, 14(2), pp. 171-191.
- Van der Voet, J., Kuipers, B. S., & Groene, S. (2015). Implementing Change in Public Organizations: The relationship between leadership and affective commitment to change in a public sector context. *Public Management Review*, 18(6), pp. 842-865.
- Van der Voet, J., Kuipers, B. S., & Groeneveld, S. (2016). Implementing Change in Public Organizations: The relationship between leadership and affective commitment to change in a public sector context. *Public Management Review*, 18(6), pp. 842-865.
- Van der Voet, J., Kuipers, B., & Groeneveld, S. (n.d.). Held back and pushed forward: leading change in a complex public sector environment". *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 28(2), pp. 290-300.
- Vera, D., & Crossan, M. (2004). Strategic Leadership and Organizational Learning. *Academy of Management Review*, 29(2), pp. 222–240.
- Vestly Bergh, L. I., Hinna, S., Leka, S., & Jain, A. (2014). Developing a performance indicator for psychosocial risk in the oil and gas industry. *Safety Science* (62), pp. 98–106.
- Wheelen, T. L., & Hunger, J. (n.d.). Strategic Management and Business Policy - Toward Global Sustainability. In *Globalization and Environmental Sustainability: Challenges to Strategic Management*. Pearson Education, Inc.
- Widerszal-Bazyl, M., & Mockało, Z. (2015). Do all types of restructuring threaten employees' well-being? An exploratory study. *International Journal Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health* , 28(4), pp. 689–706.
- Winand, M., & Anagnostopoulos, C. (n.d.). Get ready to innovate! Staff's disposition to implement service innovation in non-profit sport organisations. *International Journal of Sport Policy and Politics*, 9(4), pp. 579-595.
- Winkler, E., Busch, C., Clasen, J., & Vowinkel, J. (2015). Changes in Leadership Behaviors Predict Changes in Job Satisfaction and Well-Being in Low-Skilled

- Workers: A Longitudinal Investigation. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 22(1), pp. 72–87.
- Wynne, R., De Broeck, V., Vandebroek, K., Leka, S., Jain, A., Houtman, I., . . . Park, A.-L. (2014). *Promoting mental health in the workplace: Guidance to implementing a comprehensive approach*.
- Ylinena, M., & Gullkvist, B. (2014). The effects of organic and mechanistic control in exploratory and exploitative innovations. *Management Accounting Research* 25(25), 93– 112.
- Yuan, K. -, & Hayashi, K. (2003). Bootstrap approach to inference and power analysis based on three test statistics for covariance structure models. *British Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Psychology*, 56(1), 93-110. doi:10.1348/000711003321645368
- Zellner, A., In Keuzenkamp, H. & McAleer, M. Eds. (2001). Simplicity, Inference, and Modelling: Keeping it Sophisticatedly Simple. *Cambridge University Press*.
- Γεωργόπουλος, Ν. Β. (2006). *Στρατηγικό Μανατζμεντ*.
- Παπαδάκης. (2009). *Επίκαιρα Θέματα Στρατηγικής Επιχειρήσεων*. Αθήνα.
- Σάββας, Ε., & Κονδύλης, Ε. (1993). *Ιδιωτικοποίηση και Παραγωγικότητα*. Αθήνα: εκδόσεις Παπαζήση.
- Χυτήρης, Λ. (2001). *Οργανωσιακή Συμπεριφορά*. Αθήνα: INTERBOOKS.